

Effect of Noon Chai (Kashmiri Namkeen Tea) on the Microanatomy of Esophagus in Albino Rats: A Randomised Controlled Trial StudyShameema Gulzar¹, Rukaiya Jalal², Mohd Saleem Itoo³, Lateef Ahmad Wani⁴, Uroosa Mir F⁵¹Assistant Professor, Government Medical College Baramulla, Kashmir, India²Senior Resident, Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College Baramulla, Kashmir, India³Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy Government Medical College Srinagar, Kashmir, India⁴Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Srinagar, Kashmir, India⁵Senior Resident, Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College Baramulla, Kashmir, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** The present Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) was conducted in the Postgraduate Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College Srinagar after taking ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee.**Materials and Methods:** Fourteen albino rats weighing on an average 150 grams were taken from the animal house of Govt. Medical College Srinagar for the present study. These animals were randomly divided into 6 groups with 7 rats in each group. All groups of rats were kept under uniform husbandry condition in iron cages separately in groups. The processes of administration of these ingredients were continued for 36 weeks. The animals were sacrificed in six sittings with duration of 6 weeks between each sitting at 6th, 12th, 18th, 24th, 30th, & 36th week.**Results:** Kashmiri Namkeen Tea extract mixed with sodium chloride, and sodium bicarbonate caused premalignant changes in esophageal mucosa in the form of inflammation, Keratinisation, mucosal erosions, mucosal bleeding. These histopathological changes started to appear at 6th week and become more marked with further exposure in a duration dependent manner.**Conclusion:** Kashmiri Namkeen tea is carcinogenic; it produces premalignant changes in esophagus of Albino rats when exposure exceeds 6 weeks in a duration dependent manner.**Keywords:** Albino rats, esophageal mucosa, Histopathological Changes, Hemorrhages, Kashmiri Namkeen Tea.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The word 'te' and 'Cha' comes from China and from them comes the Persian word 'Chai' and English word Tea [1]. The tradition of tea in Kashmir came from Chinese and Turkestan. So, Kashmiri are probably one of the earliest lovers of tea. The Namkeen tea which Kashmiri consume is produced in the hills of Assam and Darjeeling and is transported to Kashmir and is available in markets as dried green leaves. Discovery of noon chai dates back to 2700 BC and it is believed completely accidental [2].

Noon chai is a traditional pink colored beverage used in Kashmir valley. It is prime traditional salted cuisine in Kashmir and almost everyone takes it twice daily. Daily intake of 2-12 cups ranges from 200-2500ml and most of the population usually likes to take hot noon chai during winter [3] According to Rohan [4], Namkeen chai or Pink tea is the most popular and

most common drink of Kashmir, and this peculiar beverage has unique method of preparation which is practised exclusively in the Valley. Green tea leaves are brewed in sodium bicarbonate in which salt is either added before or later. A correct measurement of sodium bicarbonate is a key for getting nice pink colour of tea. Formation of Red-brown colored extract called "teuth" takes about 45minutes to 2 hours of boiling till brown colour is achieved. This is then diluted with water and milk, and the salt (if not before) is added.

Dar NA et al [5] conducted a case control survey and investigated that salted tea is most commonly used beverage in Kashmir, with esophageal squamous cell carcinoma being the most common carcinoma among Kashmiri population. Similarly, Wani et al [6] stated the association between salted tea beverages and gastric cancer in Kashmir valley, and hypothesized that salt tea has a close relation

with gastric cancer. Nagini [7] suggested that the etiology of gastric cancer is multi-factorial and includes both dietary and non-dietary factors. Khuroo et al [8] stated that epidemiology of esophageal cancer in Kashmir was similar to that found in the 'Asian esophageal cancer belt, and at the same time Kashmir also had an unprecedented high incidence of gastric cancer, since Kashmiries have special personal and dietary habits, that may enhance cancer- activity.

The major diet related risk factors implicated in stomach carcinomas development include high contents of nitrates and high salt intake.

Aims and Objective

To compare the microscopic changes produced in study groups of albino rats with the microanatomy of Control Group at various stages of our research.

Materials and Methods

The present Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) was conducted in the Postgraduate Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College Srinagar after taking ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee. Fourteen albino rats weighing on an average 150 grams were taken from the animal house of Govt. Medical College Srinagar for the present study. These animals were randomly divided into two groups with 7 rats in each group. All groups of rats were kept under uniform husbandry condition in iron cages separately in groups. The processes of administration of Namkeen tea was continued for 36 weeks. The animals were sacrificed in six sitting with duration of 6 weeks between each sitting at 6th, 12th, 18th, 24th, 30th, & 36th weeks. In each sitting one rat from control & one rat from study groups were sacrificed after anaesthetizing them with chloroform. The limbs of each rat were fixed on wooden boards with pins. A midline incision was given on anterior abdominal wall and different tissues were first identified, then dissected out, cleaned and put in dishes containing formalin. These tissues were processed manually for block making using standard histological techniques; the slides were stained with haematoxylin and eosin.

Control Group: Seven rats served as control were fed on normal diet consisting of gram, vegetables and plain tap water. Study groups: Seven rats were put on combination of normal diet and Noon Chai prepared by boiling a mixture of 20 grams of tea

leaves, 4.2 grams of NaCl and 0.84 grams of NaHCO₃ in one liter of water for about 90 minutes till volume is reduced to 400ml only. In this group Noon Chai was given instead of tap water.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Apparently healthy Albino rats.
2. Albino rats with weight between 130-170grams.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Albino rats showing less physical activity and lethargic.
2. Albino rats not feeding well (refusal to feed) and suffering from diarrhea.
3. Albino rats with generalized hair loss.

Results

Normal histology of esophagus consists of 4 layers, the lining epithelium is stratified squamous non-keratinized similar to other stratified squamous epithelium of body but it does not undergo distension under stretch like other. There are 3-4 layers in the epithelium. Normal histology of rat esophagus shows non-keratinized stratified squamous epithelium resembles to human esophagus.¹⁰

Study group fed on normal diet plus extract from 20gms of dried tea leaves boiled in 1lit of water, added in it 4.2gm NaCl and 0.84gm of NaHCO₃ and boiled for >=90minutes final sum =400ml only.

Gross appearance, color, texture and morphology of esophagus were normal. On microscopic examination the histopathological changes found in the esophagus in this group of study under low power microscope were inflammatory cells in mucosa after first 6 weeks of exposure. At the end of 12th week of study changes seen were in the form of inflammatory cells in muscularis mucosa, Keratinsation, & cytoplasmic vaculation these changes were more marked at 18th & 24th week of study as shown in Fig 1 and 2. At the end of 30th week of study results observed were inflammatory cells in muscularis mucosa, Keratinsation, cytoplasmic vaculation, & dysplastic nuclei as shown in Fig. 3. At the end of 36th week of this study changes observed were Keratinsation, cytoplasmic vaculation, & enlarged nuclei as shown in table 1.

Figure 1 A microphotograph of esophagus from group F at 12thWeek showing 1-keratinisation, 2-cytoplasmic vacuolation, 3-inflammation 4-epithelial hyperplasia [Stain used H&E Magnification:10X]

Figure 2: Microphotograph of esophagus from group F at 24Week Showing 1-keratinisation, 2-cytoplasmic vacuolation, 3-inflammation 4-epithelial hyperplasia [Stain used H&E Magnification:10X]

Figure 3: Microphotograph of Esophagus from group F at 30th week showing 1.Cytoplasmic vacuolation 2. Keratinization, 3-inflammation & 4-congestion [Stain H&E Magnification: 10X]

Table 1: Results observed in microanatomy of albino rat esophagus over time period of 36 weeks by different ingredients of noon chai

Time In Weeks	Ingredients Used					
	Group: A	Group: B	Group: C	Group: D	Group: E	Group: F
	Control	On Sodium Bicarbonate	On Sodium Chloride	On Plan Green Tea Extract	On Roasted Flour	On Noon Chai
At 6 th week	No change found	Inflammatory changes were observed.	Inflammatory changes were observed.	Nil	Nil	Inflammatory changes were observed.
At 12 th week	-Do -	Keratinsation & inflammatory changes were observed.	Keratinsation, inflammatory changes, hemorrhages & epithelial hyperplasia were observed.	Keratinsation and inflammatory changes were observed.	Keratinsation and inflammatory changes were observed.	Keratinsation, inflammatory changes & cytoplasmic vacuolation were observed.
At 18 th week	-Do -	Same changes observed as in above sitting.	Same changes observed as in above sitting.	Inflammatory changes, Keratinsation, cytoplasmic vacuolation, & epithelial hyperplasia were observed.	Inflammatory changes, Keratinsation, mucosal erosions, hemorrhages, & epithelial hyperplasia were observed.	Same changes observed as in above sitting.
At 24 th week	-Do -	Same changes observed as in earlier sitting	Keratinsation & Inflammatory changes were observed.	Keratinsation observed.	Keratinsation & epithelial hyperplasia were observed.	Same changes observed as in earlier sitting.
At 30 th week	-Do -	Inflammatory changes, mucosal hemorrhages, erosions & dysplastic nuclei were observed	Keratinsation, Inflammatory changes & epithelial hyperplasia were observed.	Same changes observed as in above sitting.	Inflammatory changes, Keratinsation, Cytoplasmic vacuolation, & epithelial hyperplasia were observed.	Keratinsation, Inflammatory changes, cytoplasmic vacuolation, & dysplastic nuclei were observed
At 36 th week.	-Do -	Same changes observed as in above sitting	Same changes observed as in above sitting	Same changes observed as in earlier sitting.	Same changes observed as in above sitting.	Keratinsation, cytoplasmic vacuolation, & enlarged nuclei were observed

Discussion

Namkeen tea is a traditional beverage in the Kashmir. Since the incidence of malignancies of esophagus are very high in Kashmir region of Jammu and Kashmir. There is a widespread belief but little available literature suggesting that Namkeen tea (consists a mixture of sodium chloride, sodium bicarbonate, and green tea extract with or without milk) are important factors responsible for high incidence of GI malignancies in this region. The exact cause for high incidence of these malignancies in this region is not well known. Many theories like genetic makeup, high intake of spicy foods, pesticide exposure, and sun dried

vegetables have been implicated. The present study was conducted to observe the effects of Namkeen tea and its implicated ingredients on the microanatomy of esophagus. This is the first histological study where efforts have been made to investigate and evaluate the effect of various components of Namkeen tea excluding milk on the histology of esophagus in albino rats under laboratory conditions using low power microscope only.

Earlier case control studies [3,5,6] done at different times at different places around the valley, reported that salted tea (Kashmiri Namkeen tea) is most commonly used beverage in Kashmir, where

esophageal squamous cell carcinoma is the most common carcinoma. In the present study we used salted tea extract. We randomly selected albino rats and exposed them to oral ingestion of this extract at surrounding temperature (excluding the effect of hotness) for 36 weeks. The histopathological changes started appearing at the 6th week and become more adverse on prolonged exposure. Results observed under low power microscope at 6th week in esophagus were inflammatory changes & Keratinisation and on prolonged exposure hyperplasia, cytoplasmic vaculation, congestion & hemorrhages as shown in fig 1-3. All these histopathological observations in the microanatomy of esophagus are premalignant conditions, thus the observations of present study are in favour that Namkeen tea is an independent carcinogen. So this present study is concordant with the above workers. Similarly Hu, et al, Ishikawa et al, and Inoue et al. [9-11] in their separate experimental studies done at different times, they reported a statistically significantly positive association between tea consumption and esophageal cancer risk.

Gail Charnley et al [12] in their study stated that there is a reduction in cell yield at early time points due to the toxicity of NaCl, followed by a net increase in the number of cells in the S-phase of cell cycle at 24 hours. In our study we studied only histological changes produced after we exposed albino rats to 4.2gms of NaCl in 400ml of water continuously for 36 weeks. The histopathological results we observed were mucosal erosions, bleeding, changes in lining epithelium, nuclear changes, hyperplasia, glandular disruption & cytoplasmic vaculation, esophagus under low power microscope, these changes begins to appear after 6th week of exposure. Thus our present study is similar to above workers.

Fukushima [13] In their study they observed that oral lethal dose of salts (LD₅₀) values were higher than 4,000 mg/kg body weight compared with an inhalation study in rats using a concentration of 4.74 mg/l inhalable dust produced no deaths. High doses of NaHCO₃ promote carcinoma formation in rat urinary bladder after pre-exposure to initiator. Their study showed that NaHCO₃ has no carcinogenic effects on bladder, but the acute oral ingestion may result in a ruptured stomach due to excessive gas development. In our present study we used freshly prepared 0.84gms/400ml NaHCO₃ solution as NaHCO₃ is the most widely used chemical everywhere used by every one every day in one or another form. In our study we randomly select albino rats and expose them to oral ingestion of this solution for 36weeks. The histopathological changes observed under low power microscope at GE Junction were epithelial hyperplasia, replacement of 3-4 layered stratified squamous epithelial by multilayer stratified squamous

epithelial (18-20 layers). These histopathological are premalignant conditions in esophagus proving that sodium bicarbonate is an independent carcinogen. Thus our present study is discordant to above workers. Sloupet al [15] In their experimental study showed that Phytate is a broad-spectrum anti-neoplastic agent, affecting different cells and tissue systems, inhibit the growth of cell lines through different mechanisms of action. It was also demonstrated, that phytates has the potential to induce differentiation and maturation of malignant cells, which often results in reversion to the normal phenotype (Roasted wheat, barley or green gram reduces phytic acid by about 40 percent as phytase are destroyed by the roasting process). In our present study we randomly selected albino rats and administered them exclusively to roasted flour in semisolid form for 36 weeks. As our study is based on histopathological observations, we observed hemorrhages, metaplasia, mucosal erosions, epithelial changes, mitotic figures, and neculoraxis under low power. As these histopathological observations are premalignant changes in esophagus which shows roasted flour has a carcinogenic effect. Thus our results are concordant to earlier workers.

Conclusion

The histopathological results after administrating Namkeen tea produced premalignant changes in esophagus when albino rats were exposed to oral ingestion for first 6 weeks, further these changes become more marked on prolonged exposure. Malignant changes were not reported at any stage of study suggesting it may take more duration of exposure. The observations made in our study were concordant with earlier epidemiological studies done in Kashmir which implemented that Namkeen Tea is one of the dietary factor which is a causative agent of esophageal cancer, in our study we studied the combination itself.

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